

Secured and Privacy Preserving Data Management System for 6G Network Digital Twin

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Abstract. While the next generation mobile network, 6G, will bring new capabilities and benefits for mobile network users and operators, it will also increase the network’s complexity in management and orchestration. To address this challenge, integrating the digital twin (DT) concept into the 6G architecture has been proposed to help manage the increased complexity. However, this integration may introduce new vulnerabilities. Therefore, this study aims to identify the vulnerabilities and threats specific to the data management framework for the network digital twin (NDT) enabled 6G architecture. NDT is investigated with a focus on its security and privacy aspects, particularly from a data management perspective, through a thorough review of the currently proposed architecture. Additionally, specific threats and countermeasures to data management are identified to enable developing a 6G architecture that securely integrates the NDT framework. Moreover, the feasibility of the countermeasures is discussed for ensuring secure real-time network management, optimization, and decision-making.

Keywords: 6G, network digital twin, data management, security, privacy

1 Introduction

The concept of digital twin (DT) has gained a considerable interest from researchers and businesses due to its transformative potential in optimizing the management of physical systems. Various studies described the DT concept considering its different aspects [1], which was introduced in the early 2000s [2]. In the literature, a ‘digital twin’ term is defined as a synchronous virtual model that replicates a distinct physical object, process, service, or other abstraction [3]. It uses two-way communication between the virtual and real-world assets to update the virtual model with any new configurations, events, or changes observed in the physical world. Moreover, standardization studies are ongoing about DT’s architecture and requirements by different organizations such as International Organization for Standardization (ISO) [4], the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) [5], and the International Telecommunication Union (ITU)

[6]. Additionally, specific working groups within the Digital Twin Consortium [3] are focusing on security and dependability of DTs.

Currently, DTs are expanding into a number of domains, including networks, which gives rise to network digital twin (NDT) [7]. The NDT concept is planned to facilitate closed-loop network administration. Furthermore, NDTs are proposed to enable intent-based networking, new strategies for network security, and more efficient network maintenance and management [8]. Beside, Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) [9] and ITU [8] concentrate on developing the concepts and reference architecture for NDTs. NDT differs from a conventional network simulation by incorporating real-time data mapping and interchange between virtual and physical systems [10]. By incorporating real-time data mapping and seamless interchange between virtual and physical systems, NDT stands out as an effective network orchestration and management tool.

The data required for constructing an NDT is gathered from heterogeneous, federated environments and various types of devices, which might raise new security and privacy concerns. These concerns are often addressed in the literature, with studies focusing on threat modeling related to architectural aspects or investigating specific use-case concerns for digital twins [11]. However, further inspection of data-related concerns is required in NDT since the vast amount of data needs to be monitored, collected, or exposed in the foreseen scenarios. Moreover, data protection regulations are becoming stricter; thus, handling data-related issues is a first necessity for NDT, as with other emerging telecommunication technologies [12]. This study focuses on identifying the threats to enable the extraction of requirements for creating secure, scalable, and privacy-preserving data collection, exposure, and management processes specific to NDT-enabled 6G. In this context, reference NDT-enabled 6G architecture, threat and attack surfaces of the reference architecture, potential vulnerabilities, security and privacy concerns, countermeasures are also identified, and feasibility and applicability of these countermeasures are thoroughly discussed. In this scope, the main contributions are given below:

- Reference architecture of NDT-enabled 6G network is provided specific to the data management and data flow processes,
- Data related threat and attack surfaces are identified and classified considering the reference architecture,
- Potential vulnerabilities on corresponding attack surfaces are analyzed,
- Security and privacy concerns arising from these vulnerabilities are presented and discussed,
- Countermeasures to mitigate the risks associated with the identified threats and attacks are provided,
- The feasibility and applicability of the provided mitigation scenarios are evaluated, and the gaps in the existing literature on countermeasures are emphasized.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the system, including the reference NDT-enabled 6G network architecture and its data management processes. Section 3 analyzes the vulnerabilities within the

NDT-enabled 6G network and identifies associated threat surfaces. Then, existing countermeasures to mitigate risks arising from these potential attack surfaces are discussed, with an emphasis on their feasibility in Section 4.

2 System Overview

The telecommunications industry is one of the businesses that plans to employ NDT. The main purpose for employing NDT in the telecommunications industry is to provide simulations and predictions for various scenarios since deploying them directly on the physical network could be costly [13]. These scenarios encompasses network planning and orchestration, network slicing and resource allocation, security enhancement and threat detection, as well as testing and deploying new features. In addition to that, switching to a real-time digital replica, which is NDT, might close the performance and complexity gap in the orchestration and management of the 6G network. In this section, a high-level reference architecture for an NDT-enabled 6G network is proposed, detailed and explained considering the existing reference architectures and having slight differences on them.

2.1 NDT enabled 6G reference architecture

In the literature, several NDT architectures are proposed [8], [14], [15]. The considered NDT architecture consists of two closed-loop and three main layers as shown in Fig. 1. The first closed-loop is embedded in the unified data model for optimization and emulation (referred as inner closed-loop). The latter closed-loop is utilized for network optimization and feedback based on the three layers and referred as outer closed-loop. The three main layers shown in Fig. 1 are: *(i)* physical network layer, *(ii)* network digital twin layer, *(iii)* network application layer.

Physical network layer Any component associated with the physical network can be found within the physical network layer. This involves telecommunications operator networks, industrial IoT nodes, gNodeB, user equipment (UE), RAN, transport, and core network. Moreover, network topology, states, and processes of the network are included in this layer. Massive data flow collected from network entities and topology are sent to the NDT layer via the data collection interface. This layer can function as either end-to-end cross domain layer or as a single domain, such as core network or RAN.

Network digital twin layer This layer is located in the middle of the physical network and network application layers and has a two-way interface with those layers. This layer includes NDT functions and manages the models and the data received from the other layers. Unified data models, NDT entity management,

Fig. 1. Proposed high level NDT architecture.

and unified data repository are the three main modules that are included in this layer.

Unified data models are crucial for improving the agility and programmability of network services. This model offers prototype examples for different network applications, assuring the efficiency and dependability of change controls prior to their actuation in the real network. Data models can be categorized as either basic or functional. Basic models define the network component and structure of a network, whereas functional frameworks include network evaluation, replication, identification, extension, and validation. These models can be built and extended according to the network type, function type, and degree of generality, allowing for accurate application in various contexts. The increased variety of data models enhances the capability of the NDT to deliver robust network applications.

DT entity management is a critical function that keeps track of the life-cycle of an entity. It also visualizes and manages many network aspects, including topology, model, and security management. This entity creates virtual twin typologies, controls model instances, shows data entry, simulation, and verification procedures. Security management is responsible for controlling the safety of data,

models, and interactive systems during their entire life cycle. Furthermore, the network application layer provides input requirements to the NDT layer, which then delivers services by creating modeling instances. Upon verification, the NDT layer transmits control commands and may directly update the physical network entity to enable the quick implementation of applications such as autonomous networks [8]. On the other hand, the direct transmission of the NDT's control commands increases the risk of applying incorrect decisions. For this reason, in this study the control command from the NDT layer is represented as dashed line (Fig. 1) and transmitted through a management and control interface.

A unified data repository is responsible for data collection, storage, services, and management, as well as updating real-time data of network assets and processes.

Network application layer The network application layer is the top layer in the NDT architecture defined by ITU [8]. This layer is responsible to create the NDT instance by considering the requirements of the corresponding application. According to the specific application, all required information about the physical network layer is received by this layer. Once this information is received, it sends back the modifications and the necessary verified commands back to the physical layer through the NDT layer. Therefore, this layer paves the way to implement various network applications effectively.

3 Threat Surfaces and Analysis

Creating real-time digital replicas of the 6G network and its components expands the system's original threat landscape. Although the integration of NDT and 6G offers new opportunities and advantages it also leads to additional attack vectors, increases the risks of security breaches, and heightens privacy concerns [16]. Therefore, it is necessary to identify and categorize the attack and threat surfaces that pose security and privacy risks. These threat surfaces are determined based on the assumption that all physical and virtual components are assets. Additionally, the network's topologies within the defined NDT-enabled 6G network reference architecture are treated as entities.

This study specifically identifies and outlines threat and attack surfaces associated with the data management mechanisms, data collection, and data exposure points in a 6G network enabled by NDTs. The attack surfaces are presented and explained in the following subsections, focusing on data management within the NDT-enabled 6G network. These threat surfaces are further detailed by taking into account their components, communication mediums, involved protocols, and used interfaces. The threat and attack surfaces that are discussed in the following subsections visualized in a data flow diagram, as shown in Fig. 2.

3.1 Physical Infrastructure of the Network

The physical infrastructure of the network, which comprise various 6G network elements, actuators, sensors, IoT devices, and data collection components, is

Fig. 2. Data related threat surface is mapped into an architecture.

vulnerable to compromise. These vulnerabilities highlight the importance of ensuring the network security, particularly given their potential impact on NDT. These components are vital for the functioning of NDT-enabled 6G, as real-time data collection is essential for accurately simulating and operating in real-world conditions.

Sensors capture various types of data from the physical 6G network and transmit it to the NDT. In return, the NDT can interact with the physical 6G network [17]. Actuators located in the physical network carry out the commands arrived from the NDT. In this infrastructure, both wired and wireless communications are used. The data gathered from the physical network includes traffic data, network topology information, telemetry, logs, network management, and data related with the network [11]. Such sensitive information in the mobile network is monitored, generated, and collected to feed the NDT, which creates an attack surface for malicious actors.

The NDT system's data collection capability and functionality can be disrupted by physical damage, tampering, information disclosure, or unauthorized

access to any physical component of the 6G network. A single point of failure attack could target infrastructure elements like servers, routers, or specific devices, affecting services and normal operations. Additionally, tampered, intercepted, or stolen actuation data could lead to information leaks from mobile networks and could cause service disruptions.[18].

3.2 Communication Interfaces

The communication interface contains multiple points of vulnerability since it includes interfaces for intricate communication channels. Interactions between distinct NDTs are referred to as *inter-twin communication* while the data exchanges between the different parts and subsystems of a single NDT are referred to as *intra-twin communication*. This surface includes inter/intra-twin connections and exposure points through the data transmission between the physical network and the NDT as well as between the NDT and APIs. The communication interface controls the data flow from the physical network to the NDT to precisely reflect the state of the physical network in NDT and receive real-time updates. It also manages data transfer from the NDT to the physical network, allowing actions to be executed based on simulations and predictions made by the NDT [19].

A malicious attacker could access, intercept, and interfere with the communication between the physical network and the NDT system by performing a man-in-the-middle attack [20]. Moreover, an eavesdropping attack could be performed on the communication channels to access the transmitted data between the physical network's components or between the physical network and NDT [18]. By accessing, recording, and sniffing communication channels, attackers could extract sensitive information related to the 6G network or its NDT [11]. Furthermore, a malicious party could monitor the traffic between NDT and the physical network to save the data and re-transmit it to perform a replay attack for leading incorrect operations [21]. Besides, an attacker could establish a different identity and conceal it to conduct a spoofing attack between the traffic. Additionally, a Denial of Service (DoS) attack could target communication interfaces of devices to drain their resources, causing the NDT's functionality to fail. DoS attacks could be performed in various ways and across different layers, such as jamming in the physical layer, on-the-path attacks in the network layer, or malware injection in the application layer.

3.3 Application and Access Layer

Application and access layer function as a user interface for NDT. Therefore, this layer communicates with NDTs and contains application layer APIs to enable different NDT applications. Also, it gives vital stakeholders access to the user interfaces (UI) and simulation visualizations [22]. This layer could be identified as the most exposed area of the network and interacts directly with users and other systems, among other external entities. UI modules, visualization tools, API gateways, and all application-specific software components that access the

NDT’s functionalities are commonly located in this layer. On the other hand, this layer’s communication channels frequently consist of web-based interfaces and protocols that are accessible via internal or external networks.

An attacker might want to control the network over NDT applications by exploiting APIs. Intentionally misleading the related stakeholders that NDT serves could be achieved by manipulating the UI. On the other side, weaknesses in the software that is used to represent the simulations or results might bring out vulnerabilities. A malicious producer could perform a backdoor attack by inserting compromised programs into the provided software or hardware [18]. Ransomware attacks could be operated through the integrated software components. This might affect the way NDT operates directly. Also, an attacker could compromise the application interface to tamper with the data of NDT or the applications themselves [11].

3.4 Computation and Virtualization Infrastructure

This infrastructure includes NDT and the application & access layers shown in Fig. 2. Compromising this layer could be attractive for an attacker since any attack might eventually results in the physical layer [23]. The computation and virtualization infrastructure layer’s vulnerabilities arise from its sub-layers above. However, this layer is considered the whole digital assets of the NDT system, and the threats are classified and discussed from this point of view in the related subsections. All these threats are discussed and examined in detail under three contexts and subsections: *(i)* the computing environment where the data processed and stored (Section 3.8), *(ii)* any interface or application that NDT communicates and provides service to (Sections 3.3, 3.2), *(iii)* the computational methods that are used to process and manage the data (Sections 3.5, 3.7, 3.8).

3.5 Functional Entities

The functional entities of the proposed NDT architecture are demonstrated with dashed lines in Fig. 2. Enabling NDT requires various computational approaches, including knowledge extraction and creation algorithms, AI algorithms, and ML techniques for prediction and learning.

Therefore, the data storage and processing capabilities of computing infrastructures, from edge to cloud, are utilized to represent the models needed for a NDT and to carry out comprehensive data analytics. For this reason, the data components and the data spaces must be connected in an NDT-enabled 6G structure. Furthermore, representational tools are employed for NDT models to describe the conditions and attributes of real property [24], as well as to present the simulation and data analytics results. Eventually, utilizing software components to manage the aforementioned tasks, using massive data sets, and benefiting from different kinds of computation resources expose vulnerabilities. Identified vulnerabilities for each functional entity are presented in the Fig. 2, also mentioned and detailed in the related subsections (Sections 3.6, 3.7, 3.8).

3.6 Synchronization Process

The synchronization process is a critical attack surface in an NDT-enabled 6G network since it makes sure the virtual and physical components of the network are precisely synchronized in real-time. This synchronization includes time, volume, and frequency of data flow between the physical layer network and the NDT layer. There are two essential components of this synchronization process: (i) the physical network and its associated NDT, and (ii) dual element synchronization between multiple NDTs [25].

The first component is the synchronization between the physical network and the NDT. This synchronization directly affects having an accurate and current digital representation of the network. This requires constant data sharing, such as operational status updates, real-time network performance metrics, and configuration updates. The trustworthiness of the NDT reduces if the physical entities could not be synchronized with their digital counterparts, potentially leading to inaccurate simulations and network analysis. This misalignment could negatively affect the business value of applying NDT, as the reliability of its insights and predictions would be compromised. The second synchronization component is the synchronization of the dual elements between the multiple NDTs. This is crucial to maintain consistency between multiple NDTs, as each may represent a different section or feature of the network. This ensures accurate synchronization and analysis across the entire system. An attack to the synchronization data's integrity could be performed to force NDT to take incorrect decisions and actions. In these scenarios, an attacker might perform a replay attack or time delay attack to desynchronize the physical network and NDT to fail the all network management system [20]. Therefore, in the given architecture (Fig. 1) the possible configuration parameters from NDT layer are proposed to transmit through a control interface for minimizing this risk.

3.7 Prediction Process

AI/ML models and algorithms can simulate, predict, and optimize the network operations. Therefore, NDT incorporates AI/ML models and algorithms. These models analyze a large amount of data to predict network activity, address potential issues, and suggest potential solutions for identified problems.

The data that are used by AI/ML models are essential to ensure the models' dependability. The data must be thorough, precise, and representative of real-world situations [26]. Consequently, the datasets used for training and validation, the computing infrastructure for model training and inference, and the AI/ML algorithms themselves are the essential elements of this threat surface. The integration of AI/ML models, NDTs, and big data systems introduces specific security threats in all domains. Each technology has its own vulnerabilities that must be addressed to ensure overall system security [27]. Without strong security measures, such as secure IoT networks and protocols, these systems become vulnerable to attacks.

Attackers might launch privacy attacks to access sensitive information about the physical system by gaining access to its NDT. If the NDT includes an ML model, attackers could extract sensitive information such as model architecture, weights, or training data. Privacy attacks could also target physics-based models, allowing attackers to generate input/output data and build a surrogate model that mimics the original system. These confidentiality breaches, if successful, could result in serious threats to safety-critical applications, exposing vulnerabilities in the physical system. Furthermore, unauthorized access to sensitive data within an NDT system’s AI can lead to additional attacks or extortion. Attackers could perform model/data poisoning attacks to compel AI/ML models to make incorrect predictions and decisions. Besides, an attacker could extract private information by performing both white-box and black-box attacks on the AI/ML models [28].

3.8 Big Data Management Life Cycle

The big data management life cycle represents a diverse and intricate threat surface, encompassing multiple processes that are vital to both the physical network and its virtual counterpart. This life cycle can be divided into four stages: *(i)* large volumes of data that are collected from various sources, such as sensors, IoT devices, and other network elements, *(ii)* the data are stored in databases or cloud storage platforms, *(iii)* the data are processed and analyzed to derive meaningful insights, *(iv)* and a knowledge extraction/creation process that is conducted to transform processed data into actionable insights for decision-making [29].

Typically, high-speed networks are employed as communication channels in this threat surface, facilitating data transfer between collection points, storage facilities, and analysis platforms. These networks must be secured to prevent data flow disruption or interception. Due to the computational power required for big data processing, big data management process is often associated with cloud computing. Limited computing resources, coupled with high operational demands, can create vulnerabilities at the edges of the computing architecture, where data processed or transmitted. Stergiou et al. [29] explore the security and privacy challenges in integrating big data and cloud computing within an NDT use case, highlighting that weak authentication and access control mechanisms can lead to unauthorized access, identity theft, and data breaches.

Poor access control mechanisms in big data environments could result data breaches and privilege escalation. An attacker could perform impersonation attack and obtain unauthorized data access [18]. Inconsistent trust management and policy integration across domains introduces vulnerabilities in data sharing and communication, particularly as big data relies on diverse data sources. Additionally, improper secure-service management in big data systems—such as unpatched software or weak isolation between data streams—can increase exposure to attacks. Privacy and data protection are particularly at risk in both cloud and big data environments, where sensitive information may be exposed or misused, especially in large, multi-tenant systems. Finally, organizational security

Fig. 3. Summary of the possible attacks in the NDT architecture.

management failures, such as weak governance or inadequate security policies, are just as relevant in big data systems as they are in cloud infrastructures. This is because of the complexity of securing storage, management, and processing grows with the scale of data handled.

4 Mitigation Scenarios

The threat and attack surfaces for the data management mechanisms in NDT-enabled 6G architecture are identified and discussed. This section provides and explains overall countermeasures to mitigate the identified threats and attacks. There is always a trade-off between strengthening a system’s security and privacy measures and maintaining its utility. Therefore, the given mitigation scenarios are evaluated in terms of this trade-off as well as their feasibility and complexity.

4.1 Blockchain integration

Blockchain structure is proposed to be integrated into the NDT framework to mitigate specific threats, such as data modification, synchronization layer vulnerabilities, and the communication interface risks. The aim for this integration is to benefit from blockchain's advantages about decentralized and trust-free data storage, immutability, irreversibility, and transparency.

Blockchain-based communication and storage mechanisms within the NDT architecture are proposed to ensure data security and integrity [30], while securing the system against to the man-in-the-middle and replay attacks [31]. Blockchain is proposed to be used in authentication by storing NDT's fingerprint and signature [32]. Additionally, the data usage and access mechanisms in the NDT can be enhanced using blockchain [33]. Its distributed infrastructure also has the potential to address data dissemination problem among several parties [23].

Drawbacks of the solution Even though the integration blockchain into the NDT system might answer specific security and privacy concerns, it has challenges and bottlenecks to implement and practical usage:

- Storing an NDT inside through blockchain could be highly resource intensive, both in terms of storage capacity and computational complexity.
- Block size limitation could harden efficient data storage especially for large NDTs [34].
- In real-world scenarios a physical network and its associated NDT might needed to be updated frequently, which might require storing new signatures for each NDT snapshot. This process would increase the storage complexity due to the need for continually store new data.
- As the blockchain expands, verifying changing states may increasingly become time-consuming and cumbersome.

4.2 Decentralized and collaborative machine learning methods

An NDT receives data from various physical objects, sensor or devices to perform tasks such as security management, network orchestration, anomaly detection and prevention. Simultaneously, ML algorithms are widely utilized and has a crucial role in executing these tasks within the NDT, enabling more efficient analysis and decision-making [35]. However, these ML algorithms may necessitate the collection of all data in a central data server and training of models in a centralized behaviour, which can lead to vulnerabilities and potential threats. Therefore, the use of decentralized and collaborative machine learning methods is recommended for the NDT architecture. In particular, federated learning (FL) is proposed, since it provides a shared global model that can be trained in a collaborative manner instead of depending on a central data center for complete process of model training. In addition to that, these methods do not share private data over the network, the training process is conducted on the edge devices

and only updates are sent to the central model. For this reason, response time and risk of data breach are decreased by sending less data over the traffic [36].

Drawbacks of the solution Training models with a collaborative manner in a decentralized environment might arise new problems to deal with:

- A central server is needed to be used as aggregator which might be an attractive attack point for an attacker to perform single point of failure.
- It eases the participation of malicious users, a user could perform a false data injection attack by sending false weight to the central server.
- This solution might require management of different data incorporated from various edge devices.
- Since this solution requires end user to consume their computational power, incentives might be required to motivate edge devices to involve the training process [37].

4.3 Blockchain integrated federated learning

FL is able to solve the problems arise from central model training process by enabling distributed collaborative training. However, FL still needs a central server to aggregate the global model and has to deal with the risk that are coming from having a central server as it is discussed in the previous subsection. Therefore, it is proposed to use blockchain for transferring data in decentralized learning scenarios to guarantee the data authenticity and integrity while mitigating the risks associated with the central aggregation server [38].

The blockchain-enabled FL process for the NDT structure could be summarized as follow [39]: FL tasks are announced on the blockchain, allowing trainers to select their tasks, download the global model, and begin working with their local data. System states and local model updates are linked to the physical trainers and uploaded to the blockchain. Miners verify the updates and aggregate them. This aggregation is followed by a consensus mechanism to aggregate all updates into a newly created block. If consensus achieved, the newly created block is added to the blockchain. The process ends when the task publisher finishes the task or the predetermined rounds are accessed.

Drawbacks of the solution While this solution reduces the risks arise from the centralized aggregation and improve the data integrity and security, it still has significant drawbacks [39], [40]:

- A miner cannot simultaneously check multiple trainers' local modal updates, leading to increased verification time, which significantly reduces throughput.
- The trade-off between the practicality of the blockchain-based FL and privacy preservation is still a challenge, since the trainers face an increased computational load.

- This solution increases the communication latency since the trainers are edge devices which have restricted communication source [36].
- The trainers are expected to work on non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) data, which directly affects the applicability of blockchain-enabled FL systems [39]. This non-IID can increase the complexity training phase and reduce the effectiveness of collaboration among the trainers.
- The reliability of the task publisher remains questionable, as discussed in previous mitigation strategies (Sections 4.1, 4.2). A malicious user could join the system and compromise the model training [40].
- The challenge of motivating trainers to involve into the training process propagates by the integration of blockchain (Section 4.1), and FL usage (Section 4.2).

4.4 Lightweight and scalable encryption algorithms

NDT-enabled 6G architecture includes multi-domain heterogeneous environments, each with unique security and privacy requirements as well as varying computation limitations. Consequently, there are various encryption schemes that are proposed to be used within the NDT architecture, tailored to different interfaces and prioritized according to specific needs [41], [29].

Drawbacks of the solution Having lightweight encryption algorithms through an NDT might enhance the performance, reduce latency, and ease real-time data processing; however, these advantages come with drawbacks:

- This solution might require use case, interface or computation resource specific approaches to effectively address the challenges within different requirements and environments.
- A hasty development process might lead to the further vulnerabilities.

4.5 New security protocols

A number of authentication protocols have been developed to be used in the NDT architecture, including blockchain-based two-factor, three-factor authentication protocols [31], [42]. These authentication protocols are varying from each other by their prioritization of security and privacy aspects. The three-factor authentication protocol is specifically designed to mitigate vulnerabilities found in two-factor authentication, such as impersonation, offline password guessing, session-specific temporary information attacks.

Drawbacks of the solution Even though the aforementioned efforts improves the authentication process, there are still drawbacks and trade-offs related to complexity.

- The blockchain based solutions outlined above still need a trusted third party for tasks like private key registration, participant’s registration, which diminishes the decentralized system’s benefits and architecture.
- The improvements still inherits the drawbacks of blockchain systems, such as high computational demands and storage requirements, which raise concerns about the overall practicality of these solutions.

4.6 Privacy enhancing solutions

NDTs rely heavily on real-time data and advanced AI models to simulate, predict, and optimize the network’s behaviors. However, these NDTs are vulnerable to AI privacy attacks, such as model inversion, data poisoning, and membership inference attacks. Several defenses, known as Privacy Enhancing Techniques (PET), can be used to mitigate privacy attacks, including anonymization, encryption, and differential privacy [27, 43]. For query-based privacy attacks, a straightforward defense is limiting the number of allowed model queries. Anonymization can be applied to remove personally identifiable information. Homomorphic encryption offers another safeguard by enabling computations on encrypted data without revealing the underlying information. Differential privacy (DP) adds noise to training data, model parameters, or outputs to protect against reconstruction attacks. Additionally, model watermarking can be employed to safeguard a model’s intellectual property (IP) rights [27].

Drawbacks of the solutions The solutions proposed to preserve privacy might have drawbacks from various perspectives, including computational complexity, storage limitations, scalability issues, or reduced performance as listed below:

- Sophisticated attacks can still re-identify individuals by combining anonymized data with auxiliary datasets. Removing identifiable information may reduce the usefulness of the data for analysis or model training, especially when anonymization is too strict. Anonymization can be less effective for complex datasets where patterns can be inferred without explicit identifiers.
- Homomorphic encryption is computationally expensive, leading to significant performance bottlenecks, especially for large datasets or complex models. Encryption adds processing time, making real-time or near-real-time applications more challenging. Moreover, it’s complex to implement and maintain, requiring specialized expertise and resources.
- Utilizing differential privacy adds noise to data, parameters, or model outputs can reduce the accuracy and performance of the model. It can be difficult to balance privacy protection with data utility, as the level of noise needs to be carefully tuned.
- Restricting the number of queries can limit the usability of the system, especially for legitimate users who may need multiple queries to interact effectively with the model. Attackers could still perform effective privacy attacks within the allowed query limit by using more advanced query techniques or distributing queries across multiple accounts.

- Watermarking can increase the model’s size or slightly reduce its efficiency, depending on the technique used. Skilled adversaries can reverse-engineer models to remove watermarks, especially if the watermarking method is not robust.

5 Discussion

This study delves into the security and privacy issues that arise from the integration of physical network to DT. An NDT system includes heterogeneous physical part of the network, a real-time reflected digital replica and an application layer designed to serve related stakeholders. Apart from the other studies, these studies specifically cover the security and privacy concerns associated with the data management systems within the reference an NDT enabled 6G architecture. The identified threat and attack surfaces for the data management system within an NDT enabled 6G architecture are summarized and visualized in the given Fig 3. As shown in the figure, several attacks are classified based on the layers considered in NDT-enabled 6G architecture. This leads to differentiate the impact of the attacks in each layer which enables to take countermeasures against the attackers. Furthermore, relevant mitigation scenarios for identified threats and attacks are studied. Also, the applicability of the mitigation strategies are discussed while considering the complexity, feasibility, resiliency and scalability of the whole NDT enabled 6G system.

6 Conclusion

Efforts to optimize the performance of the 6G network, increase its efficiency, predict potential issues, and secure the entire 6G network architecture are growing as next-generation networks evolve. As a solution, integrating NDTs into 6G networks is proposed to optimize, orchestrate and simplify network management. However, this integration introduces new threat surfaces, bringing additional security and privacy concerns. This paper presented a brief exploration and investigation of the NDT-enabled 6G reference architecture. Based on this architecture, a high-level investigation was conducted, covering both data and computation aspects. Furthermore, a thorough analysis of potential threats to the NDT-enabled 6G network was performed, and various potential attack types are explored and discussed. Finally, relevant mitigation scenarios for identified threats and attacks are studied considering their feasibility on a real-world NDT-enabled 6G architecture. For future work, specific use cases can be identified, and their security and privacy implications analyzed alongside appropriate mitigation strategies. Additionally, the trade-off between security requirements and the overhead of the proposed solutions can be better evaluated through these use-case scenarios.

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